

${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ transitions, respectively in the order of increasing energy³. The bands occurring beyond 34000 cm^{-1} have been assigned as charge transfer bands to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2u}$ transition³. The band occurring at ~ 30000 and 32000 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (C=S) and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (C=N) transitions⁴ of the ligands. The single electron parameters Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 for these complexes come out to be 20920, 9172, 4637 and 22420, 11532, 3717, respectively.

The strong bands occurring at 3680 cm^{-1} in their spectra of $C_{16}H_{15}NSO$ and at 3650 cm^{-1} in their spectra of $C_{16}H_{17}NSO_2$ may be assigned to OH stretching vibrations. These bands seem to disappear in the spectra of the chelates forming (M-O) bond. The phenolic (C-O) stretching vibration in the ligands occurs as strong band in the region $1200\text{--}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. On chelation, this band is shifted to higher frequency. The bands resulting from the ligands $C_{16}H_{15}NSO$ and $C_{16}H_{17}NSO_2$ at 1590 and 1620 cm^{-1} correspond to $\nu(C=N)$ vibrations⁵. A sharp negative shift in $\nu(C=N)$ to 1530 and 1600 cm^{-1} , respectively in the complexes of the two ligands indicates the involvement of the nitrogen atom in bond formation with Pd(II) atom. The disappearance of the stretching frequency of -SH observed in the free ligands at 2560 and 2570 cm^{-1} , clearly indicates the loss of thionic proton on coordination and formation of a new bond between metal and sulphur. Both the complexes showed a broad band in the region $3400\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating the presence of a water molecule. It is thus inferred that the ligands acting as tridentate occupy three positions on Pd^{2+} ion while the fourth is occupied by a water molecule.

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Alkali Metal Complexes : Adducts of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with 1,10-Phenanthroline

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THE interaction of alkali metal salts of organic acids with 1,10-phenanthroline has been investigated¹⁻³. We describe here the synthesis and

characterisation of a number of solid adducts of alkali metal salts of acetylacetonone, salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with the title ligand. They have the general formula ML_nL (M=Li, Na or K; L=deprotonated acetylacetonone, salicylaldehyde or *o*-hydroxyacetophenone; $n=1$ and $L'=1,10$ -phenanthroline). Elemental analyses, thermal, ir spectral and the solution studies of these solid adducts reveal that they are genuine complexes.

Experimental

Our usual method of synthesising these adducts was to take a suspension of an alkali metal salt in benzene in a test-tube and then to add 1,10-phenanthroline to it in 1:3 mole ratio. On stirring the mixture slowly, all the solids went into solution. The contents were then warmed for 5 min on a steam bath and cooled, when crystals of the adducts came apart. These were filtered, washed with cold benzene and dried in an electric oven at 80° .

Results and Discussion

The adducts of alkali metal salts of acetylacetonone, salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with 1,10-phenanthroline are white, bright yellow and light yellow, respectively.

Almost all the compounds are stable when stored under dry conditions. The transition/decomposition temperatures of all these adducts (except those of alkali metal salts of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone) are much higher than the melting point of the ligand. This seems to indicate that 1,10-phenanthroline in the adducts is essentially not present as free base or even as its hydrate, which melts at 117° and $93\text{--}94^\circ$, respectively and that the compounds are held together by forces stronger than the van der Waals forces.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared measurements of all the compounds were carried out in the region $4000\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in Nujol mulls.

The pertinent bands in the ir spectrum of 1,10-phenanthroline are 1505 , 854 and 738 cm^{-1} . The 1505 cm^{-1} band is the most intense band in the $1650\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and is attributed to $\nu CC + \nu CN$ vibrations⁴. On complexation, this band shifts to a higher frequency by $5\text{--}10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and also exhibits a weak satellite on its low frequency side. The bands in the region $900\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are identified with motions of the ring hydrogen atoms moving in phase out-of-the-plane of the ring. The frequency at which absorption occurs will depend upon the number of adjacent hydrogen atoms around the ring. Since phenanthroline has three rings two of which are equivalent with three hydrogen atoms, and one with two adjacent hydrogen atoms, only two bands are observed, one at 738 cm^{-1} (assigned to out-of-plane motion of the H-atoms on the heterocyclic rings) and the other at 854 cm^{-1} (assigned to out-of-plane motion of hydrogen atoms on the

central ring). On complexation, the multiple splittings of these two bands arise from out-of-plane motions other than those in phase and also probably from overtones of low lying fundamentals in resonance. The splitting of these two bands appears to be metal sensitive.

These facts suggest a coordination of the alkali metals with 1,10-phenanthroline through the nitrogen atoms of its pyridine fragments.

The ir spectra of these adducts point to the absence of hydrogen bonding in them, showing thereby that hydrogen bonding between a chelating ligand and the alkali metal salt of a chelate anion is not necessary for formation of the adducts.

Conductivities :

Molar conductivities of all the adducts were measured in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone at 25° at a concentration of 10^{-3} M. The solvent was calibrated by Banerjee *et al*⁵ and they observed that the values of molar conductivities in the range 35-40 cm^{-1} correspond to 1 : 1 electrolyte.

It is observed from the results that none of the values approach either ideal or 1 : 1 electrolyte. Low values of molar conductivities of these adducts seem to indicate neutral complexes. The trend $\text{Li} < \text{Na} < \text{K}$ would indicate that the lithium complex is the strongest in solution.

Probable structure :

The above discussion suggests the coordination of the ligand 1,10-phenanthroline with alkali metals through nitrogen atoms of the pyridine fragments. Accordingly, these adducts should have the following structure :

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Metal Derivatives of Organo-Antimony Compounds : Reactions of Anhydrous Chlorides of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with Arylantimony Compounds

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IN continuation of our study on the reactions between arylantimony compounds and anhydrous metal chlorides¹⁻³, we report here the reactions of manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) chlorides with tetraphenylstibonium chloride.

Experimental

The hydrated metal chlorides (B.D.H. or Sarabhai Chemicals) were dehydrated⁴ by refluxing them with thionyl chloride and the anhydrous metal chlorides thus obtained were used after analyses. Triphenylstibine was prepared by Wurtz reaction from antimony trichloride, benzene and sodium metal⁵. Tetraphenylstibonium chloride was prepared by the known method⁶. Solvents were dried and deoxygenated before use. Because of the hygroscopic nature of some of the reactants, all preparations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Dry nitrogen gas was flushed into the reaction mixture to maintain an inert atmosphere.

Preparation of quaternary stibonium complexes : A general method was employed for preparing the quaternary stibonium complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) chlorides using the stoichiometric amounts of the reactants.

To a dry alcoholic or acetonitrile solution of anhydrous metal chloride was added slowly and dropwise, a solution of tetraphenylstibonium chloride in benzene or alcohol under dry nitrogen atmosphere with constant shaking at room temperature. No heat evolved during the mixing of the reactants. Nitrogen gas was passed for 5 to 10 hr with occasional shaking. The solution was concentrated by evaporating the solvent under reduced pressure. The flask was stoppered and kept aside when solid compound started depositing slowly. The supernatant was decanted into another flask after keeping the reaction mixture for a day or two. The compound was washed with dry benzene (2-3 times) and finally with *n*-hexane. It was then dried *in vacuo* (1-2 mm) for 2 hr. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Reaction of anhydrous copper(II) chloride with triphenylstibine : To a dry benzene solution of anhydrous cupric chloride was added benzene solution of triphenylstibine slowly and with constant stirring under dry nitrogen atmosphere. After 20-24 hr, a white solid started depositing which was found